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Imparting Peace and Values through Education

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Article History:

Received: 30-03-2017

Accepted: 30-03-2017

Published: 31-03-2017

Keywords:

Education, Peace, Values

Article code: OJMR316

Access online at: www.ojmr.in

Source of support: Nil

Conflict of interest: None declared

Indexed in: Open J-Gate, Indian Science, Google Scholar, Scientific Indexing Services

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Summary:

Peace and values have an important part of education since Vedic times in this country. It has been also the practice in other countries from the time of Plato and Aristotle in Greek history. There are many approaches to peace and value education, many of which are based on ideology, practical experience, and good intentions. Peace and values are more relevant in view of the recent terrorist attack on World Trade Centre, attack on Indian Parliament, and the mounting tension for show down between India-Pakistan, US, Russia and Syria at present. This paper aims to describe the idea through which peace and values can be imparted.

Background

We are living in the period of rapid changes. Advancement and worldly progress without development of deep feeling in the man's heart is causing hell on the earth. Now, the world is facing greatest pitfalls, are the moral decay, breakdown of traditions. The danger is that we have learned how to split the bomb rather than, how to serve mankind. In ancient era, Indian education is based on the Vedas, which only depicts our inner potentials. But globalization has produced a metamorphosis in self-images, and goals among educational institution around the world by which education become commercial. Through the passes of time, we have seen from gurukul education to digital education.

Education is one of the instruments to empower children to live peacefully and also to build peace and unity in the world, to be citizens and leaders of tomorrow. We need to develop in them the sensitivity towards peace, the awareness, that violence and retaliation are not the ways of resolving disagreements. Value education is subsumed in education for peace, but is not identical with it. Peace is a contextually appropriate and pedagogically gainful point of coherence for values. It concretises the purpose of values. The responsibility for building a peaceful and enlightened society rests with the educator (Pant & Gulati, 2010).

Only this view of education involves the total development of the person, and not a finished product or outcome of a specific curricula for a given time or location.

Peace

The term "peace" does not merely imply the absence of overt violence (sometimes referred to as negative peace). It also encompasses the presence of social, economic and political justice, which is essential to the notion of "positive peace" (Hicks, 1985). Pant & Gulati (2010) coded that each one has to find his peace from within, and peace to be real must be unaffected by outside circumstances (Mahatma Gandhi, p.23). The word "peace" in the English language is derived from the Latin "pax", meaning agreement or contract (Ostrowski, 2014). Peace is a dynamic, not a static process. The level of peace constantly increases or decreases with the actions of each relevant party. It is an active process, not a passive state. Building and maintaining peace takes active involvement. Peace involves not only living in harmony with oneself but also with others, including nature. It is true that peace begins with individuals, who are calm within.

So, one can begin understanding peace from 'the peace within self' perspective. The Preamble to the Constitution of UNESCO (1945) declares that since wars

begin in the minds of men, it is in the minds of men that the defences of peace must be constructed.

Values and related views

The inclination for choosing peace also depends on the values, we hold. Our choosing the course to peace will reflect our values and the way, we perceive the world and people. When we think of our values, we think of, what is important to us in life? Each of us holds numerous values (e.g., achievement, security, benevolence) with varying degrees of importance (Schwartz, 2006). These values may be different according to the circumstances and situations of individuals. The German philosopher Friedrich Nietzsche used first the word “values” in 1880 (Sharma and Katoch, 2007). Although the root of word “Value” might remotely have been drawn from “worthiness”. In ancient Indian canons, you will find such appropriate expressions as Dharma, Shila, Sadachara, Niti, etc. But the word “Mulya” is never found in our classical literature to convey the meaning of “Morality”. A wide accepted concept of value in traditional philosophy is “Truth, Goodness, Beauty”, the “Satyam, Shivam, Sundaram”.

Values are the guiding principles of life which are conducive to all round development. They give direction, firmness to life and bring joy, satisfaction and peace to life (Venkataiah, 2007). They are beliefs linked inextricably to affect. When values are activated, they

become infused with feeling (Schwartz, 2006). Human core values like Love (*Prema*), Truth (*Satya*), Righteousness (*Dharma*), Non-Violence (*Ahimsa*) and Peace (*Shanti*) should form the bedrock of Indian life. All other values subsume to these five core values of human life.

Education for Peace and Values

Montessori (as cited in NCERT, 2006, p.3) stated that “All education is for peace”. Education for peace, as distinguished from peace education, acknowledges the goal of promoting a culture of peace as the purpose shaping the enterprise of education. Education for peace is education for life, and not merely training for a livelihood (NCERT, 2006). Equipping individuals with the values, skills and attitudes they need to be wholesome persons, who live in harmony with others and as responsible citizens is the goal of education for peace. If we are to teach real peace in the world, we shall have to begin with children (NCERT, 2006, p.3). Consequently, here I consider some aspects of education for peace in the light of what I have discussed earlier.

Education for peace is supposed to be the idea, strategy for contextualizing, and operationalizing ethical and moral values. It is the process of promoting the knowledge, skills, attitudes, and values needed to bring about behaviour changes that will enable children, youth and adults to prevent conflict and violence.

Education for peace seeks to nurture ethical development, inculcating the values, attitudes and skills required for living in harmony with oneself and with others, including nature. (NCF, 2005) It is about helping students to understand and transform conflict in their own lives, in the community and in the world at large. It is part of all learning areas and reinforced by people treating each other in positive ways in classrooms, playgrounds and in their families and communities. Education for peace is a precondition for national in view of growing intolerance and violence (Sharma, 2013).

Education for value is a process of education and focuses on the development of critical thinking; rational choice and action, respecting the autonomy of the learner. Inculcates a sense of humanism, a deep concern for the well-being of others and for the nation in children. This can be accomplished only, when be instill in the children a deep feeling of commitment to values, that would build this country and bring back to the people pride in work that brings order, security and assured progress. Through value education we would like to develop the social, moral, aesthetic and spiritual sides of a person, which are often underestimated in modern education. Aurobindo (1997) defined that there is a side of thought, of idea, of upward will & souls aspiration; there is a side of creative self-expression, appreciative, aesthetic, intelligence and imagination; and there is a higher thinker which views us mind's pure set, largest

and most general formulation of its consciousness of life and its dynamic view of existence. Imparting values and peace education is suggested not as a separate subjects of study at any stage but has to be judiciously integrated with all subjects in the scholastic areas and other activities in non-scholastic areas.

Suggestions

After having critical analysis of the terms and their operational implications in the light of above stated points, we can formulate a programme of action which can be suitable to institutions.

- 1. Holistic approach:** Education for peace and value requires a holistic and integrated approach. This approach proposes that all teaching-learning activities and interactions, whether in the class or outside, must be inspired by the comprehensive aims of education, which are inclusive of peace education, recognized and self-esteem is strengthened are valuable.
- 2. Harmony with nature:** Peace and value both are like a seed. It sprouts, becomes a sapling, grows into a tree and spreads its branches all around, offering shelter and shade. Peace and value start with the individual, moves on to the family and community, reorienting systems, structures and institutions, spreading throughout

the land and ultimately, embracing planet earth, as a whole (Pant & Gulati, 2010). Living together in harmony as one of the four pillars of education (Delor, 1996).

3. Increasing intrinsic motivation:

Coon and Mitterer (2007) found that people who are intrinsically motivated usually get personally involved in tasks, which leads to greater creativity (Nakamura & Crikszentmihalyi). Excessive competition is detrimental to peace and value. Inherent in competition is a set of values wherein success depends upon beating and defeating others. What is valued? Is triumph over others and being number one? Respecting ideas and questions criticism and making fun of children's remarks can hinder them from expressing themselves.

4. Positive reinforcement:

Positive reinforcement is considered more effective than negative reinforcement for desirable behavior (McInerney, 2007). Positive reinforcement, where accomplishments (behavioural as well as academic) are appropriately.

5. Social service:

Social service projects should be integral part of education. Voluntary social service and participation in philanthropic initiatives mature one's

compassion and help reduce negative traits (e.g., anger, arrogance, selfishness etc.).

6. Teachings of Yoga:

The Sanskrit word "yog" comes from the root 'yug', means to join. The aim of teaching of Yog is to develop self-control and the intellect. Ancient Indian rishis were very well aware of this truth. Patanjali found yoga as that, which restrains the thought process and makes the mind serene. Regular practice of fundamental teachings of Yog, generate and preserve human vital power; making body and mind clam at-ease state. Patanjali suggests that ethics (yama and niyama) is the way to cleanse the mind, imbibing peace and values at all three stages (e.g., body, mind and spirit). There are various styles of Yog (e.g., yama, niyama, asana, pranayama, prathyahara, dharana, dyaana and samadhi), each has specific characteristics that reflect a particular approach.

Apart from this all educational institutions should lay emphasis on attitude building of tyaga (renunciation) for human welfare, protective of nature and sacrifice for the motherland. Everybody should have the feel of responsibility towards one's own duties and should be accountable to at least himself. Most important instead of mere talking about education for values, we should live value to set examples for

others. Formation of national character should be the goal of education in a multi-national, multi-religious, multi-lingual and multi-cultural society like ours. For this, educational institutions should introduce special activities and programmes for infusing spirit of National consciousness, National spirit and strengthening strong collective well for the security, integrity and development of motherland.

Conclusion

Peace and values based education are necessary for our present education system. Through peace and values, we seek the real knowledge and goal of life in righteous manner. It is equally important

in the students and also in parents, because parents also play crucial role to develop the personality of child. Involvement of parents and elders in the family and society is vital in imparting of moral and cultural values. Lama (n.d.) stated that one nation's problems can no longer be satisfactorily solved by itself alone; too much depends on the interest, attitude, and cooperation of other nations. A universal humanitarian approach to world problems seems the only sound basis for world peace. Actually, we do not need to put in any great efforts to make our lives simpler. A small change in our education and behavior can subside the perturbation of our life and make it serene and beautiful.

References

1. Agrawal, V. (2013). Flashback: Parliament Attack 2001. India Times, Retrieved from <http://www.indiatimes.com>
2. Aurobindo, S. (1997). The Renaissance in India and Other Essays on Indian Culture (1st ed., Vol. 20). Pondicherry, Pondicherry: Sri Aurobindo Ashram Press, 97-104.
3. Coon, D. & Mitterer, J. O. (2007). Introduction to Psychology: Gateways to Mind and Behavior (11th ed.). New Delhi: Cengage Learning, 387-425.
4. Delors, J. (1996). Learning the Treasure within: Report of International Commission on Education for the 21st Century. Paris: UNESCO.
5. Grunward, M. (2001). Terrorists Hijack 4 Airliners, Destroy World Trade Center, Hit Pentagon; Hundreds Dead. The Washington Post, Retrieved from <http://www.washingtonpost.com>
6. Hicks, D. (1985). Education for Peace: Issues, Dilemmas and Alternatives. Lancaster: St. Martin's College.
7. Lama, H. D. (n.d.). A Human Approach to World Peace. Retrieved April 10, 2016, from <http://www.dalailama.com/messages/world-peace/a-human-approach-to-peace>
8. McInerney, D. M. (2007). Educational Psychology: Constructing Learning. Australia: Pearson Higher Education, 171-206.

9. National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT) (2005). National Curriculum Framework for School Education. New Delhi: NCERT, 2-61.
10. National Council of Educational Research and Training (NCERT). (2006). Position Paper National Group on Education for Peace New Delhi: NCERT, 3-43.
11. Ostrowski, J. (2014). The Myth of Democratic Peace: Why Democracy cannot deliver peace in the 21st Century. *The Journal of Peace, Prosperity and Freedom* (3), 11-83.
12. Pandya, P. (Ed.). (2015, November/December). Education: Perspective & Possibilities for Future. *Akhand Jyoti*, 13(06), 13-18.
13. Pant, D. & Gulati, S. (2010). *Way to Peace: A Resource Book for Teachers*. New Delhi: NCERT, 23-111.
14. Schwartz, S. H. (2006). *Basic Human Values: Theory, Measurement and Applications*. The Hebrew University of Jerusalem, 06-42.
15. Sharma, A. (2013). Education for Peace: Transforming the culture of Violence. Retrieved from <http://www.spaceandculture.in/index.php/spaceandculture/article/view/15/5>
16. Sharma, Y.K. (2007). *Education for Values, Environment and Human Rights*. New Delhi: Deep & Deep Publication, 02-08.
17. UNESCO. (1945). Preamble to the Constitution of the United Nations Educational, Scientific and Cultural Organization. Retrieved March 08, 2016, from http://portal.unesco.org/en/ev.php-URL_ID=15244&URL_DO=DO_TOPIC&URL_SECTION=201.html
18. Venkataiah, N. (2007). *Value Education-An Overview*. New Delhi: A P H Publishing Corporation, 01-08.

How to cite this article:

Pal, J. K. and Vishwakarma, S. K. (2017). **Imparting Peace and Values through Education**. *Online Journal of Multidisciplinary Research*, 3(1): 63-69.